

The incorporation of a metal catalyst for the ammonia synthesis in a ferroelectric packed-bed plasma reactor: does it really matter?

Paula Navascués,^{*a} Juan Garrido-García,^a José Cotrino,^{a,b} Agustín R. González-Elipe^a and Ana Gómez-Ramírez^{*a,b}

^a Laboratory of Nanotechnology on Surfaces and Plasma. Instituto de Ciencia de Materiales de Sevilla (CSIC-Universidad de Sevilla), Avda. Américo Vespucio 49, E-41092 Seville, Spain.

^b Departamento de Física Atómica, Molecular y Nuclear, Universidad de Sevilla, Avda. Reina Mercedes, E-41012 Seville, Spain

* Corresponding authors

anamgr@us.es

paula.navascues@icmse.csic.es

Keywords (5-8): ammonia synthesis, nonthermal plasmas, plasma-catalysis, packed-bed reactors, ferroelectric barrier discharge, ruthenium catalyst.

Abstract

Plasma-catalysis has been proposed as a potential alternative for the synthesis of ammonia. Studies in this area focus on the reaction mechanisms and the apparent synergy existing between processes occurring in the plasma phase and on the surface of the catalytic material. In the present study we approach this problem using a parallel-plate packed-bed reactor with the gap between the electrodes filled with pellets of Lead Zirconate Titanate (PZT), with this ferroelectric material modified with a coating layer of alumina powder (i.e., Al₂O₃/PZT) and the same alumina powder incorporating ruthenium nanoparticles (i.e., Ru-Al₂O₃/PZT). At ambient temperature the electrical behavior of the ferroelectric packed-bed reactor differed for these three types of barriers, with the plasma current reaching a maximum when using Ru-Al₂O₃/PZT pellets. A systematic analysis of the reaction yield and energy efficiency for the ammonia synthesis reaction, at ambient temperature and at 190°C and various electrical operating conditions, has demonstrated that the yield and the energy efficiency for the ammonia synthesis do not significantly improve when including ruthenium particles, even at temperatures at which an incipient catalytic activity could be inferred. Besides disregarding a net plasma-catalysis effect, reaction results highlight the positive role of the ferroelectric PZT as moderator of the discharge, that of Ru particles as plasma hot points and that of the Al₂O₃ coating as a plasma cooling down dielectric layer.

INTRODUCTION

Ammonia is a strategic compound because of its central role to produce nitrogen fertilizers, which are indispensable to increase the crops productivity in order to feed the growing world population. It is also deemed a suitable and safe hydrogen vector and therefore a strategic compound for the energy ecosystem transformation. Currently, ammonia is obtained through the catalytically-driven Haber-Bosch process, which proceeds at high pressures and temperatures with yields around 15-20%.¹ Today, ammonia production exceeds 150 Mt per year, it is responsible for 1.2% of the worldwide greenhouse gases emission,²⁻⁴ and consumes ca. 2% of the world energy supply.⁵ In the race to make the chemical industry more sustainable (i.e., free from CO₂ emissions) and compatible with intermittent electricity sources, the search for alternative procedures to produce ammonia has become a key topical issue. In this context, plasma technology has emerged as an attractive candidate for the ammonia synthesis because it offers mild operation conditions (ambient temperature and atmospheric pressure), easiness to scale-up the reactors and the possibility to operate in a distributed way directly connected to the grid or to decentralized small-scale renewable power plants.⁶

Among the different plasma technologies used for the NH₃ synthesis (e.g., gliding arc discharges,⁷ plasma jets,⁸ or RF discharges⁹) packed-bed plasma processes are being widely investigated since the reactors permit the direct incorporation of a catalyst in the barrier, a combination that has been claimed to render superior process performance.¹⁰ Nevertheless, the reason(s) for this apparent synergy is still a debatable trending question¹¹ and an appealing challenge to the plasma-catalysis community. For example, although the kind of metal used as catalyst,¹² the type of support,¹³ its dielectric constant,¹⁴ mesoporosity,⁵ specific surface area¹⁵ or even its size¹⁶ are known to influence the plasma-catalyst interaction, and hence the reaction kinetics and yields, there is not yet a clear understanding of the effect of each particular parameter, thus hampering the systematic design of more efficient plasma-catalyst systems.

Many authors have worked in the selection of appropriated catalysts for the plasma-assisted synthesis of NH₃. In this regard, G. Akay and K. Zhang obtained a 12% nitrogen conversion using a porous Ni-based catalyst in a discharge moderated by glass and BaTiO₃ pellets¹⁷ X. Tu and collaborators have recently studied the effect of incorporating a metal catalyst into BaTiO₃ pellets, obtaining energy efficiency values higher than 2 g NH₃/kWh when using nickel particles.¹² M. Carreon and coworkers have reported that perovskites with electronegative alkaline-earth cations (e.g., MgTiO₃) contribute to weaken the nitrogen bond (N≡N) and thereby favor the ammonia synthesis reaction.¹⁴ These authors have also demonstrated that mesoporous materials such as zeolites

seem to favor the ammonia synthesis.^{18,19} Similar results have been obtained by Y. Wang *et al.* using a Ni catalyst supported on a mesoporous MCM-41 support⁵ and by K.H.R. Rouwenhorst *et al.*²⁰, using zeolite 4A as adsorbent. Proposed explanations for the positive role of nanoporous materials as catalysts assume that the adsorption of the formed ammonia molecules in porous structures prevents their decomposition, (i.e., the reverse reaction, $2\text{NH}_3 \rightarrow 3\text{H}_2 + \text{N}_2$ (1), which can be promoted by plasma electrons). Recently, we have also demonstrated that inefficient reactions involving hydrogen exchange processes (e.g., $\text{NH}_3 + \text{H}_2 \rightarrow \text{NH}_2\text{H} + \text{H}_2$ (2)) can also take place in packed-bed reactors, contributing to decrease the energy efficiency of the synthesis reaction.²¹

However, despite the significant contributions to this topic, there are not clear criteria for the choice of suitable catalysts to work under plasma conditions, particularly because plasma catalysts might be different materials than those used for conventional thermal catalytic reactions. In this regard, Bogaerts and coworkers have combined a catalytic microkinetic model with a plasma chemical kinetics description²² and concluded that the NH_3 turnover frequency (TOF) does not depend on the type of catalytic material in plasmas with a high concentration of radical species. This conclusion differs from that in other studies proposing that the TOF depends on the type of catalyst.^{15,23,24} In this line, an experimental works by Gorbanev *et al.*, using Al_2O_3 -supported Fe, Ru, Co, and Cu catalysts, showed that the reaction yield of ammonia, although always lower than 1%, was up to four time higher when comparing efficiencies for metal catalyst and those obtained with bare Al_2O_3 beads as barrier.²⁵ Similarly, Gorky *et al.* found an increase in efficiency upon addition of Ni particles to a packed-bed reactor filled with SiO_2 pellets.¹⁶ However, the meager reaction yields around 0.5% reported in this latter study makes the evidence inconclusive owing to this very low ammonia yield.

This controversial scenario in relation with the role of metal particles in the plasma-driven ammonia synthesis reactions rises critical questions about the possible links between surface and plasma mechanisms and the extent by which metals may affect the plasma properties and behavior.^{26–28} In other words, although adding a metal catalyst to the packed-material could promote catalytic-driven processes, this might also modify the electric field in the immediacy of the metal nanoparticles, alter the characteristics of the discharge and likely affect the reaction mechanisms in the plasma phase. A first objective of the present work, beyond the existence of possible catalytic effects, is to determine the occurrence of plasma effects induced by the presence of metal nanoparticles in the packed bed and how these effects may affect the efficiency of the ammonia synthesis process. A second related objective is the verification of possible modifications in the

moderator role of a ferroelectric barrier formed by packed pellets of Lead Zirconate Titanate (PZT), a high dielectric constant material with a high Curie temperature that in previous works has demonstrated a high efficiency for ammonia synthesis^{29–31} and other plasma-driven reactions.^{32–34}

To discuss the possible effects of the incorporation of metal particles on the performance of the ferroelectric reactor, as well as to address other relevant mechanistic aspects of the synthesis process, particularly the possible existence of catalytic driven mechanisms, ammonia reaction yield and energy efficiency of the plasma reaction are taken as relevant magnitudes for analysis. With this purpose, we study the effect of incorporating a ruthenium (Ru) metal catalyst, one of the most widely used metal catalyst for the thermal and plasma-catalytic synthesis of ammonia,^{13,22,23,25,35–37} into the ferroelectric barrier. This study has been complemented with the Optical Emission Spectroscopy (OES) analysis of the plasma discharge. A comparative analysis has been carried out using three configurations of the barrier: (i) normal PZT pellets (designed as PZT configuration); (ii) PZT pellets covered by an Al₂O₃ coating (Al₂O₃/PZT configuration), and (iii) PZT pellets with the alumina coating containing Ru nanoparticles (Ru-Al₂O₃/PZT configuration). The results obtained demonstrate that the incorporation of ruthenium nanoparticles does not provide a significant enhancement (or this is negligible) either in reaction yield or in energy efficiency with respect to the PZT barrier, even working at temperatures as high as 190°C, known to define a threshold for plasma-catalysis ammonia synthesis using ruthenium as catalyst.³⁷ A critical assessment of the reaction mechanisms supports that, although ruthenium may contribute to produce more intense plasmas by modifying the electric properties of the discharge it can be also detrimental for the ammonia synthesis through the promotion of undesired reactions (i.e., the aforementioned ammonia decomposition or hydrogen exchange processes). All these processes seem to hide possible catalytic effects induced by the ruthenium nanoparticles. It is also concluded that the synergy found when incorporating ruthenium to the ferroelectric barrier reactor could be also obtained when using any kind of metal, instead of the high-cost catalyst usually employed for thermal catalysis.

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Experimental system

The packed-bed reactor used in this work has been described in previous publications and readers are addressed to these articles and to the **Supporting Information S1** for a complete description of the experimental set-up.^{21,29,31} The reactor consists of two

stainless steel electrodes of 75 mm diameter separated by a gap of 5 mm where pellets of the ferroelectric PZT are placed. PZT pellets (with a mean diameter in the range of 0.5-2 mm) were prepared in our laboratory upon the high temperature sintering of powders of this material supplied by APC International Ltd. (USA), as described in a previous article.³² PZT was chosen as ferroelectric barrier material because it has demonstrated to have a better performance for the ammonia synthesis than the more widely utilized BaTiO₃ ferroelectric.²⁹ Moreover, Curie temperatures of 332 °C for the former vs. 120 °C for the latter ensure that PZT ferroelectric properties are preserved at high operating temperatures.³⁸ The bottom electrode was grounded and the upper one was connected to a high voltage power amplifier (Trek Inc., USA, Model PD05034), coupled to an AC function generator (Stanford Research Systems, USA, Model DS345). To electrically characterize the discharge, we used an oscilloscope (Agilent Tech., USA, Model DSO-X 3924A) directly connected to a high voltage probe to measure the applied voltage. To collect the transferred charge or the current we used a capacitor (2.51 μF) or a resistance (223 Ω) in series with the plasma reactor when the experiments were carried out at ambient or high temperature, respectively. When the capacitor was used, a current monitor (Pearson, USA, Model 6585) was ground connected to measure the current. The area of the Lissajous curves (plot of transferred charge vs. applied voltage) was taken as a measurement of the average consumed power in each experiment. Two series of experiments were performed at ambient temperature: firstly, we varied the applied voltage amplitude between 1.75 and 3 kV at a fixed frequency of 5 kHz; secondly, we varied the frequency between 1 and 5 kHz at a fixed voltage of 2.5 kV. This latter procedure induces a progressive change in the plasma current and was chosen as a method to vary systematically the plasma power without modifying the electric field distribution in the packed-bed reactor.

All the experiments have been carried out at atmospheric pressure. Some experiments were performed at ambient temperature (a small drift up to 40°C under steady state conditions could be detected, an issue that has been considered for energy efficiency calculations) and others at 190 °C, as determined by a thermocouple placed at the external walls of the reactor. To achieve these high temperature conditions, the stainless-steel reactor was wrapped with heating ribbons activated by a temperature heating control device. At ambient temperature, the frequency was varied between 1-5 kHz, while for the 190°C-experiments it was varied between 1 and 3 kHz (keeping constant the voltage at 2.5 kV) because of experimental limitations: at high temperatures the appearance of sparks and short-circuits affected the stability of the plasma at frequencies higher than 3 kHz.

As inlet gases we used nitrogen and hydrogen (Air Liquid, Spain, Alphagaz). A total flow rate of 23 sccm and a N₂:H₂ ratio of 1:3 was kept constant during all the experiments. To ensure that the residence time of the reactant gases in the reactor was similar when varying the temperature, we adjusted the gas flow considering the expected volume expansion due to their heating inside the reactor. N₂ and H₂ gas flows were set at 5.75 sccm and 17.25 sccm at ambient temperature and at 3.7 sccm and 11.1 sccm at 190°C, respectively.

A quadrupole mass spectrometer (Pfeiffer Vacuum, Germany, QMG 220 Prisma Plus) was used to analyze the reaction products. The reaction yield, which accounts for the amount of nitrogen transformed into ammonia, was defined as follows: ^{21,29,31}

$$N_2 \text{ conversion (\%)} = \frac{Q_{NH_3}(\text{out}) [\text{sccm}]}{2 \cdot Q_{N_2}(\text{in})[\text{sccm}]} \cdot 100 \quad (\text{E1})$$

where $Q_{NH_3}(\text{out})$ and $Q_{N_2}(\text{in})$ are the flow rates of the produced ammonia and the nitrogen feeding the reactor, respectively. The energy efficiency of the synthesis process is defined as the ratio between the amount of produced ammonia and the consumed energy: ^{21,29,31}

$$EE - NH_3 [\text{gNH}_3 \cdot (\text{kWh})^{-1}] = \frac{m_{NH_3}(\text{out}) [\text{g} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}] \cdot 60 [\text{min} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}]}{\text{Power} [\text{kW}]} \quad (\text{E2})$$

where $m_{NH_3}(\text{out})$ refers to the mass (in grams per minute) of produced ammonia. This evaluation of NH₃ mass from the outlet flow takes into account the average temperature of the reactor during each experiment. We should indicate that temperature was measured at the reactor walls and that values of this parameter may be slightly higher in the interior of the reactor.

Optical Emission Spectra (OES) were recorded with a monochromator (Horiba Ltd., Japan, Jobin-Yvon FHR640) with a resolution of 0.2 nm. The light emitted by the plasma was collected by an optical fiber feedthrough situated at the lateral wall of the reactor, pointing to the inter-electrode space (see details of the diagnosis in **Supporting Information S1**).

Preparation and characterization of coated PZT pellets

In this study, we have investigated the effects of combining high-dielectric constant ferroelectric pellets (PZT) with a dielectric Al₂O₃ coating loaded with metal nanoparticles.

Al_2O_3 powder was used as support for the metal catalyst due to its high surface area, which allows a good dispersion of the Ru nanoparticles. From an electrical point of view, it is noteworthy that its dielectric constant – around 10 – is much lower than that of the PZT – around 1900.

A Ru- Al_2O_3 catalyst powder prepared by wet impregnation was incorporated onto the PZT pellets. For comparative purposes the PZT pellets were also covered with just the Al_2O_3 powder. To prepare the Al_2O_3 /PZT pellets, the Al_2O_3 powder (Sigma Aldrich, γ - Al_2O_3 with a BET surface area of $120 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$) was water impregnated (using an incipient wetting impregnation technique) and the resulted slurry was used to cover the PZT pellets. For the Al_2O_3 -supported Ru catalyst, the coating process was done using a solution of Ruthenium (III) chloride hydrate (Sigma Aldrich) instead of water. Approximately 5 mL of a ruthenium chloride solution (63 mg/mL) was needed to incorporate a 2 wt% Ru loading into 7 g of Al_2O_3 powder. After covering the pellets with the corresponding slurry, they were kept at ambient temperature during 12h. Then, following the procedure described by B. Patil,³⁹ the pellets were dried in air at 120°C for 4h, reaching this temperature with a heating ramp of $1^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ to evaporate the water in a smooth way. Finally, the resulting pellets were calcined in air at 450°C for 3 hours, applying a ramp rate of $2^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. After this calcination treatment, ruthenium should be in an oxidized form, but it becomes reduced to metal nanoparticles upon exposure in the reactor to the reducing N_2+H_2 plasma. This chemical transformation should be quite fast and occur during the first few seconds of reactor operation.

The coated pellets and the Al_2O_3 and Ru- Al_2O_3 powders were characterized by means of scanning electron microscopy (SEM) using a S4800 field emission microscope (Hitachi High-Tech Corporation) equipped with an energy dispersive X-Ray analyzer at 30 kV (EDX, Bruker-X Flash-4010). The Al_2O_3 and Ru- Al_2O_3 powders were also characterized by means of transmission electron microscopy (TEM) using a JEOL 2100Plus microscope (Japan) operated at 200kV. Surface characteristics of coated pellets and powder samples were determined by X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS) using a PHOIBOS 100 (Specs, Germany) spectrometer operating at normal incidence. The $\text{K}\alpha$ line of Aluminum was utilized to collect the spectra. The Binding Energy (BE) scale was referenced to the C1s line of spurious carbon taken at 284.6 eV. The BET surface area of the PZT, Al_2O_3 /PZT and Ru- Al_2O_3 /PZT pellets were measured by means of a TriStar II 3020 analyzer (Micromeritics Instruments Corporation, US). Surface area of the Al_2O_3 and Ru- Al_2O_3 powders were also determined. Prior to the analysis, all the samples were outgassed at 150°C for 2 hours.

Packed-bed barrier configurations.

The $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{PZT}$ and $\text{Ru-Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{PZT}$ pellets were introduced in the packed-bed as a compact layer in the middle of the barrier, sandwiched by two layers of PZT pellets. This configuration avoids possible short-circuits due to local discharges and electrical contact between Ru particles and the metal electrodes. The central layer of coated pellets had a volume of 11.5 cm^3 , while the top and bottom layers of PZT pellets occupy a total volume of 27 cm^3 . The sketches in **Figure 1** show schematically the differences between the three kinds of pellets, as well as between the barrier architectures of the packed-bed reactor for each configuration.

Figure 1. (a) Schematic of PZT, $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{PZT}$ and $\text{Ru-Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{PZT}$ pellets; (b) arrangements of the sets of pellets for the used barrier configurations. Ground and HV (high voltage) symbols refer to the electrical connections of bottom and top electrodes.

The effect of covering the PZT pellets with an alumina coating has been analyzed with the AC/DC module of Comsol Multiphysics.⁴⁰ Simulations have been carried out for an inter-electrode distance of 3.695 mm, assuming that the PZT pellets are irregular and have a mean radius of 0.6 mm. To disregard any electric field variation due to differences in the pellet surface geometry, the external shape profile of the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{PZT}$ is taken identical to that of the PZT pellets but incorporating an irregular alumina coating with a mean thickness of 0.05 mm (see **Supporting Information S2** for a more detailed description of the simulation procedure). The applied voltage between the electrodes was 2.5 kV at a frequency of 5 kHz. An extremely fine mesh was used for the calculations, rendering a computing time of approximately 90 seconds. The color maps in **Figure 2(a)** (top) depict the electrical field distribution between two PZT pellets (i.e., PZT configuration) and (bottom) between adjacent PZT and $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{PZT}$ pellets (note that in the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{PZT}$ configuration only the middle layer in the packed-bed is filled with

coated pellets). These color maps evidence that, for similar outer topographies and distances, the electric field in the inter-pellet space is higher between two PZT pellets than between a PZT and an adjacent Al₂O₃/PZT pellet, as revealed by the evaluation of the electric field along the line “r” connecting two pellets (see **Figure 2(b)**).

Figure 2. Analysis of the electric field distribution in the packed-bed barrier by means of Comsol Multiphysics simulations.⁴⁰ (a) Distribution of the electric field between two equally separated pellets of PZT (top) and a PZT and a Al₂O₃/PZT pellet (bottom). The “r” line indicates the straight line selected to evaluate the electric field. (b) Electric field distribution along the line “r” for the PZT and Al₂O₃/PZT configurations.

The differences in electric field distribution in the inter-pellet space for the PZT and PZT-Al₂O₃/PZT configurations respond to the distinct dielectric constants of the ferroelectric PZT and dielectric Al₂O₃ materials.³⁸ Interestingly, the electric field intensity appears enhanced at locations where either the Al₂O₃ or the PZT surfaces present irregularities.

The influence of asperities and irregularities is usually overlooked for similar simulations in the literature, where perfectly spherical inter-electrode pellets are usually considered for the calculations.^{41,42} These simulations of electrical field distribution forecast that the lower electric field in the inter-pellet space for the Al₂O₃/PZT configuration may affect the electrical behavior of the reactor. In concrete, according to these results, this configuration is expected to *cool down* the plasma, reducing both the electron temperature and density.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Characterization of Al₂O₃/PZT and Ru-Al₂O₃/PZT Pellets

The morphological characteristics of the Ru-Al₂O₃/PZT pellets are shown in **Figure 3**, displaying a series of SEM micrographs and EDX maps of a pellet and its coating. Considering the amount of material used during the wet impregnation process we can estimate a coating thickness of approximately 0.05 mm, in case that it were homogenous. This corresponds to a 21 % of the total pellets volume. A cross section schematic drawing of a Ru-Al₂O₃/PZT pellet is shown in **Figure 3(a)**. This scheme shows that the coating is irregular and that the Ru nanoparticles are not only located at the external surfaces of the agglomerated Al₂O₃ powder, but also embedded in pores and between alumina particles in the interior of the irregular alumina coating layer. The micrograph in **Figure 3(b)** shows that the coating is not entirely conformal and that the pellet may expose areas of uncovered PZT. A similar topology was found for the Al₂O₃/PZT pellets. Additional evidence of this topology is gained by XPS analysis of the surface state of pellets. Data in the **Supporting Information S3** show that alumina is the majority surface component, although a non-negligible contribution of PZT (i.e., signals due to Pb, Ti and Zr) are also detected, indicating that the pellet surface is not fully covered by the catalyst. Meanwhile, the EDX/SEM analysis of the Ru-Al₂O₃ powders demonstrates that Ru was concentrated in certain zones of the Al₂O₃ powder support, as evidenced in **Figures 3(c) and (d)**. The SEM micrograph in **Figure 3(c)** shows that Ru is distributed in the interior the Al₂O₃ grains, likely in the pores, as well as irregularly segregated in the form of aggregates at certain regions, as indicated by arrows in the figure. This is also clearly seen in **Figure 3(d)**, showing EDX maps of the same powders demonstrating that, in certain zones, Ru may form clusters within the alumina support. The presence of Ru at the surface of the Al₂O₃ support was also demonstrated by XPS analysis (see **Supporting Information S4**). The size of Ru-particle aggregates has been estimated by performing a statistical analysis by TEM micrographs (using the ImageJ software) taken for different Ru-Al₂O₃ powder samples. This analysis renders a mean

value of 120 ± 6 nm for the aggregates, the individual ruthenium nanoparticles having a much smaller size. This aggregate size is higher than that of nanoparticles prepared by using chemical reduction processes, as reported in the literature⁴³ (see Supporting Information S4). We should note that aggregation state of nanoparticles would not significantly affect their catalytic activity, which would be mainly determined by the density of surface-active catalysts sites, regardless of the aggregation state of the nanoparticles.

Figure 3. (a) Sketch and (b) SEM micrographs of a Ru-Al₂O₃ coated PZT pellet. The dots in sketch (a) refer to Ru aggregates and the fact that it is distributed in the interior of the alumina coating layer. (c) SEM micrograph and (d) EDX analysis in the form of Al (red) and Ru (green) maps of the Al₂O₃-supported Ru catalyst powder.

From the point of view of the potential catalytic activity and plasma behavior of the Ru-Al₂O₃/PZT pellets, it is also noteworthy that Ru is not only located at the external surface of the pellets, but also embedded within the Al₂O₃ particles and in its internal pores. This distribution is not equivalent to that commonly utilized in theoretical works to model the effect of the metallic phase in packed-bed systems, where metal particles are usually located at the external surface of the pellets.⁴⁴

The BET surface area of the sintered PZT pellets was 0.7426 m²/g, while it was 3.9854 m²/g and 5.8014 m²/g for the Al₂O₃/PZT and Ru-Al₂O₃/PZT pellets, respectively. As

expected, due to the alumina coating, the surface area of the covered PZT pellets ($\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{PZT}$ and $\text{Ru-Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{PZT}$ configurations) increases, in agreement with the high surface area of the alumina powder. The difference between the two is likely due to a distinct amount of coating material in each case.

Electrical Behavior of the Packed-bed Reactor

The characteristic $I(t)$ curves measured at ambient temperature and at 190°C were used to characterize the electrical behavior of the packed-bed reactor working in the PZT, $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{PZT}$ and $\text{Ru-Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{PZT}$ configurations. **Figures 4(a)** and **(b)** depict these curves recorded at 2.5 kV for experiments at ambient temperature (5 kHz) and 190°C (2 kHz). **Figure 4(a)** shows that, although the three $I(t)$ curves depict the typical microdischarge features of packed-bed reactors, the overall intensity varies at ambient temperature according to $\text{Ru-Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{PZT} > \text{PZT} > \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{PZT}$. This is confirmed by the Lissajous plots depicted in **Figure 4(c)**, where it is apparent that the discharge power, taken as proportional to the area, is maximum for the reactor containing $\text{Ru-Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{PZT}$ pellets, followed by PZT and $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{PZT}$ pellets. The increase in plasma current found for the $\text{Ru-Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{PZT}$ pellets can be interpreted in the frame of recent model studies of plasma discharges taking place in metal particles decorating dielectric pellets: according to Kruszelnicki *et al.*,⁴⁴ when metal particles are incorporated onto dielectric beads in packed-bed reactors operated at atmospheric pressure there is an enhancement in plasma density in the proximity of the metal component. This effect was studied by the authors using a computational model and experimentally confirmed by iCCD imaging analysis. A similar effect is to be expected for the $\text{Ru-Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{PZT}$ pellets, where Ru nanoparticles would act as plasma hot spots inducing a local change in electrical field and an increase in plasma electron density and energy.

Meanwhile, the minimum current and consumed power found for the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{PZT}$ configuration agrees with the Comsol analysis discussed above, and it can be explained admitting that the Al_2O_3 coating, with a much lower dielectric constant than PZT, tends to *cool down* the plasma due to a decrease in the electric field intensity in the inter-pellet space. In line with these considerations, Lissajous figures reported in **Figure 4(c)** for the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{PZT}$ configuration depict a smaller slope for both the cell (upper and lower lines in the figure) and the packing material capacitance (right and left side-lines), in agreement with the lower dielectric constant of Al_2O_3 as compared to PZT.⁴⁵ Lissajous Curves obtained at different voltages are shown in **Supporting Information S5**, proving that plasma volume increases with the applied voltage.

The picture described in the previous paragraphs for the reactor operating at ambient temperature, changed at 190°C . In fact, unlike the relatively large differences in $I(t)$ for

the three configurations observed at ambient temperature, **Figure 4(b)** shows that the $I(t)$ curves tend to overlap at 190°C, with just slightly lower values for the Al₂O₃/PZT configuration. We attribute this behavior to the progressive non-linear increase with temperature of the dielectric constant of PZT. In other words, the significantly higher value of the dielectric constant of PZT at 190°C would be the predominant factor controlling the electrical response of the reactor. In agreement with this assessment, Lissajous plots shown in **Figure 4(d)** confirm that power consumption is similar for the three plasma reactor configurations operated at 190°C.

Figure 4. Electrical characterization of the reactor for the three barrier configurations (PZT, Al₂O₃/PZT and Ru-Al₂O₃/PZT). $I(t)$ curves during plasma ignition at (a) ambient temperature (2.5 kV, 5 kHz) and (b) 190°C (2.5 kV, 2 kHz); (c, d) Lissajous plots determined from the curves in (a) and (b), respectively.

Ammonia Synthesis at Ambient Temperature

The ammonia synthesis from N₂+H₂ plasmas has been firstly investigated at ambient temperature for the three barrier configurations of the packed-bed plasma reactor.

Figure 5 shows the evolution with the applied voltage of reaction yield (i.e., N_2 conversion) and energy efficiency. According to **Figure 5(a)** reaction yields smaller than 0.5% were obtained at low voltages for the three barriers. The uncertainty in accurately determining such little values of reaction yields and their correspondingly low consumed power values make inaccurate the determination of the energy efficiency. Accordingly, the points for these low voltage experiments in **Figure 5(b)** are represented with empty dots joined by dashed lines to clearly distinguish these results from those that are meaningful for the analysis of the reactor performance. In this sense, data in **Figure 5(a)** for voltages equal and higher than 2.25 kV show that the reaction yield is higher for the reactor filled with PZT pellets. Interestingly, there is a similar high yield for the Ru- Al_2O_3 /PZT configuration, except for the highest accessible voltage at which the conversion yield tends to decrease. The lowest yield values are obtained for the Al_2O_3 /PZT reactor configuration, a result that can be related to the lower current intensity as observed in the Lissajous curves (cf. **Figure 4**) and the lower electric field distribution between pellets deduced by COMSOL simulation (cf. **Figure 2**).

Figure 5. Evolution at ambient temperature of (a) the reaction yield and (b) the energy efficiency for the NH_3 synthesis reaction as a function of the applied voltage. Data

corresponding to low reaction yields are plotted with empty dots and dash lines. Experiments were carried out at a frequency of 5 kHz. The star dot corresponds to a 7% nitrogen conversion in experiments reported in ref. ³¹

From a practical point of view, the energy efficiency of a plasma-catalysis process defines its actual capacity to compete with other established technologies. ⁴⁶ It is noteworthy in this regard that high conversion yields do not warrant high energy efficiencies, and that an opposite evolution of these two magnitudes is a common behavior for different plasma catalysis processes. ^{12,47,48} An example illustrating this tendency is included in **Figure 5(b)**. The star dot in the diagram corresponds to operating conditions taken from a previous study of our research group ³¹ (i.e., a PZT barrier of 3 mm, flow rate of 11.5 sccm, frequency of 5 kHz, and voltage amplitude of 2.5 kV), where a N₂ conversion yield of 7% was obtained. We realize here that this high conversion rate occurs at expenses of a relatively small energy efficiency in comparison with the conditions herein described, where a barrier of 5 mm includes a middle layer of pellets loaded with the Al₂O₃-supported metal catalyst (c.f., **Figure 1**).

The evolution of the energy efficiency with the applied voltage shown in **Figure 5(b)** reveals a different behavior depending on reactor configuration, therefore suggesting some differences in reaction mechanisms. The Al₂O₃/PZT configuration depicts an approximately constant value of the energy efficiency for voltages higher than 2.25 kV, indicating that reaction mechanisms do not significantly change with the applied voltage. Meanwhile, the PZT barrier depicts an energy efficiency maximum at 2.5 kV, followed by a progressive small decrease at higher voltages. We tentatively attribute this decrease to the occurrence of inefficient processes such as the decomposition of ammonia and hydrogen exchange reactions. ²¹ The tendency is similar for the Ru-Al₂O₃/PZT configuration and voltages higher than 2.25 kV, but always with lower efficiencies than for the PZT case. Since the reaction was carried out at ambient temperature, *pure catalytic* mechanisms induced by the Ru particles can be discarded. We propose that this systematic lower efficiency can be related to a higher probability of ammonia decomposition reactions induced by the impact with high-energy electrons generated in the microdischarges due to the presence of the metal phase (see in **Figure 4(a)** a higher current amplitude for the Ru-Al₂O₃/PZT configuration)⁴⁴. Meanwhile, for the Al₂O₃/PZT configuration, we assume that ammonia decomposition and/or hydrogen exchange reactions responsible to diminish the energy efficiency for the ammonia synthesis are less probable because of the claimed *cooling down* of the plasma for this configuration.

The previous considerations gain further credit examining the evolution of reaction yield and energy efficiency as a function of operating frequency (c.f., **Figure 6**). The frequency was varied systematically (1-5 kHz) at constant voltage (2.5 kV) as a way to modify the power consumed in the reactor (see **Supporting Information S6**). **Figure 6(a)** shows that, in the three cases, the reaction yield progressively increases with frequency (i.e., power or current), although following different tendencies. The increment with the frequency is more noticeable in the case of Ru-Al₂O₃/PZT and PZT configurations, while in the case of the Al₂O₃/PZT configuration the slope of the curve is less pronounced, the values following the order Ru-Al₂O₃/PZT>PZT>Al₂O₃/PZT. Additionally, the evolution of the energy efficiency shown in **Figure 6(b)** reveals that this magnitude continuously increases for the PZT configuration, but it passes through a maximum (at around 2.5 kV) for the Ru-Al₂O₃/PZT one. Meanwhile, for the Al₂O₃/PZT configuration the energy efficiency reaches a maximum at a frequency of 3 kHz. This behavior supports that, for the Ru-Al₂O₃/PZT configuration, inefficient reaction mechanisms (the reverse ammonia decomposition reaction (1)) or hydrogen exchange processes, reaction (2)) are favored at increasing frequencies (i.e., consumed powers), something that is less evident for the PZT configuration, where the energy efficiency continuously increases with frequency. In this experiment, a maximum efficiency of 1 g NH₃/kWh was found at 5 kHz for the PZT configuration. According to the previous analysis, the maximum energy efficiency found for the Al₂O₃/PZT configuration at 3 kHz (1.3 g NH₃/kWh) can be linked with a relatively lower probability of decomposition reactions under these conditions, or, in other words, to that the power (or current) increase with frequency does not favor the occurrence of decomposition reactions for the Al₂O₃/PZT configuration.

Figure 6. Evolution of (a) reaction yield and (b) energy efficiency for the ammonia synthesis reaction as a function of frequency. For the experiments at 1 kHz, results are plotted with empty dots and dash lines indicating a possible inaccuracy in the determination of these values. Experiments were carried out at ambient temperature, a voltage amplitude of 2.5 kV and a variable frequency between 1 and 5 kHz.

Ammonia Synthesis at Elevated Temperature

Within a plasma-catalysis perspective, a certain catalytic effect associated to the Ru particles might be expected at elevated temperatures.³⁷ Therefore, similar experiments than those described in the previous section were carried out at a temperature of 190°C (measured at the reactor wall). According to Rouwenhorst *et al.*, this temperature is a kind of threshold for the catalytic promotion of the ammonia synthesis in plasma reactors incorporating a Ru-based catalyst.³⁷ Owing to the specific conditions of our experiment, it is expected that the temperature inside the packed-bed zone may be higher than this nominal value at the reactor wall.⁴⁹

Since an applied voltage of 2.5 kV provided the highest energy efficiency at ambient temperature (c.f., **Figure 5**), the 190°C-experiments were carried out at this voltage varying the frequency between 1 and 3 kHz. The electrical characterization of the reactor under these operating conditions reported in **Figures 4(b,d)** and **Supporting Information S7** shows that at high temperature current and power values increase with the frequency for all the configurations, but that this increase is slightly less pronounced for the Al₂O₃/PZT configuration. **Figure 7** shows the evolution with frequency of the reaction yield and energy efficiency at 190 °C (values obtained at ambient temperature, c.f. **Figure 6(b)**, are also plotted for comparative purposes). In **Figure 7(a)** it can be observed that reaction yields significantly increase with respect to the yields obtained at ambient temperature, with values five times higher at 3 kHz and practically no differences between the three reactor configurations (in a similar way to the behavior found for the electrical response of the reactor). Remarkably, up to frequencies of 2 kHz, the energy efficiency increases (see **Figure 7(b)**), presenting significant differences depending on the configuration, following the order Ru-Al₂O₃/PZT < PZT < Al₂O₃/PZT. Then, for the PZT and Al₂O₃/PZT configurations, energy efficiency decreases at higher frequencies, while it remains still growing for the Ru-Al₂O₃/PZT configuration. We tentatively attribute the decrease in energy efficiency for the PZT configuration at 3 kHz to a progressive increase in the occurrence of inefficient processes (the mentioned hydrogen atom exchanges (2) and ammonia decomposition (1)). A similar small decrease is obtained at this frequency for the Al₂O₃/PZT configuration. Meanwhile, the different evolution found for the Ru-Al₂O₃/PZT configuration at frequencies higher than 2 kHz suggests changes in the reaction mechanisms, likely due to the appearance of new plasma-catalytic reaction pathways involving the Ru particles.³⁷ In agreement with different authors, those reaction mechanisms could involve the dissociative adsorption of N₂ molecules²³ and the adsorption of vibrational excited nitrogen molecules that can interact with H or H₂ species from the plasma (or adsorbed on the metal surface) to form adsorbed NH* species on the catalyst surface.^{5,15} However, the small differences found in reaction yield between the three barriers (c.f., **Figure 7(a)**) suggest that possible catalytic surface effects should be considered second-order or negligible with respect to other reaction pathways. This behavior differs from that of a typical catalytic process where the adsorption and surface dissociation of N₂ and/or H₂ molecules are required steps for the thermal catalytic synthesis of ammonia.^{1,36,37,50,51}

For pure thermal catalytic processes, activation energies determined using Arrhenius plots are around 60-115 kJ/mol depending on the promoters used during the process.⁵¹ For the plasma-catalytic synthesis of ammonia lower values obtained for different Ru-

based catalysts were 20-40 kJ/mol.⁵² Claimed interpretation of this lower activation energy is that plasma contributes to excite the nitrogen molecule, favoring its dissociation on the catalyst site. Our results above suggest that this effect is negligible and that the electrical characteristic of the discharge is the most important factor affecting reaction efficiency. This view is also supported by previous results with PZT showing that the rate limiting step for the ammonia synthesis is the NH^* formation in the plasma gas phase.³⁰

Figure 7. Evolution of (a) reaction yield and (b) energy efficiency for the ammonia synthesis reaction as a function of frequency. Experiments were carried out at 190°C for a voltage amplitude of 2.5 kV and variable frequencies between 1 and 3 kHz. For comparison, data obtained under the same operating conditions at ambient temperature are included in the plot as dashed lines and mild colors.

As well as activation energy, turn over frequency (TOF) is a typical magnitude utilized to discuss catalytic efficiencies. It has been also used for plasma catalysis processes where values around 10^{-3} - 10^{-2} s⁻¹ have been reported for the ammonia synthesis reaction.⁵² A rough calculation of TOF referred to the amount of Ru in the Ru-Al₂O₃/PZT pellets rendered values around $4 \cdot 10^{-4}$ s⁻¹, slightly lower than those obtained in these works.

However, we would like to stress that calculation of TOF makes sense for cases where reactions take place at the surface of the catalysts. Our results above strongly suggest a negligible contribution of surface catalytic effects to the overall reaction process, disregarding such kind of calculations. A similar critical view was discussed by other authors for plasma-catalysis processed.²²

OES Analysis: Intermediate Plasma Species at Ambient and Elevated Temperature

To further analyze the differences between the three configurations at ambient and high temperatures and gain insights on the reaction mechanisms, we have completed the previous study with optical emission measurements. **Figure 8** shows the optical emission spectra acquired for the three configurations at (a) ambient temperature and (b) 190 °C. As observed, the following bands can be detected: NH^* (transition [$A^3\Pi \rightarrow X^3\Sigma^-$] at 336 nm), the first negative system of N_2^+ (transition [$B^2\Sigma_u^+ \rightarrow X^2\Sigma_g^+$], with main bands at 391.4 and 427.8 nm), and the second positive system of N_2 (transition [$C^3\Pi \rightarrow B^3\Pi$], with main bands at 337 and 357.9 nm).

Figure 8. OES spectra recorded at (a) ambient temperature (2.5 kV, 5 kHz) and (b) 190°C (2.5 kV, 2 kHz).

Previous studies of our research group^{29,31} and other authors¹⁸ with N₂ and H₂ plasmas indicate that the presence of N₂⁺ species in the gas phase is a required intermediate for the ammonia synthesis process, while NH* excited species can be associated with both synthesis and decomposition processes of ammonia. In particular, using the same reactor that herein and applying an isotope labelling methodology, we demonstrated that a nitrogen alone plasma does not render ammonia molecules, even if the pellet surface is previously saturated with hydrogen atoms. To obtain ammonia molecules it is necessary to add hydrogen to the gas phase.²¹ Thus, we propose that the formation of NH* species in the plasma is a rate-limiting step for the ammonia synthesis. Based on these premises on the role of detected plasma species, we propose the following plasma mechanistic scheme for the synthesis of ammonia:

Note that hydrogenation reactions (5-7) might take place in the plasma gas phase, on the surface of the packed material (i.e., through a L-H mechanisms), or also through the interaction of NH* species from the plasma with H atoms adsorbed on the surface of metal particles or exposed zones of PZT (E-R mechanisms). L-H and E-R mechanisms entail surface catalytic process, which we consider negligible in our case. Although no emission lines corresponding to atomic nitrogen are detected by OES, formation of NH* in the plasma phase could also start from processes such as (8) or (9):

Looking at the spectra in **Figure 8**, at ambient and elevated temperatures, there are slightly differences in the ratio between bands and therefore in the relative concentration of species in the plasma phase. At first glance, it is observed that band associated to the N₂⁺ at 190 °C presents a higher intensity that those obtained at room temperature and that, for both cases (room and elevated temperature) the N₂⁺ band intensity measured for the Al₂O₃/PZT configuration is smaller than for the other two configurations (PZT and Ru-Al₂O₃/PZT). To analyze this fact, we evaluate the normalized N₂⁺ relative emission

intensity, i.e., the N_2^+/N_2^* ratio by supposing that the ration between band height is equivalent to the ratio between the concentration of the excited emitting species. At ambient temperature (5 kHz, 2.5 kV), the intensity ratios were 0.90, 0.49 and 0.82 for the PZT, Al_2O_3/PZT and $Ru-Al_2O_3/PZT$ configurations, respectively, while values of 0.98, 0.75 and 0.87 were found at 190°C (2 kHz, 2.5 kV). Most remarkable is that at ambient temperature the N_2^+ relative emission intensity was smaller for the Al_2O_3/PZT configuration. Since the formation of N_2^+ species requires electrons with energies equal or higher than 15.6 eV,⁵³ the lower population of this excited specie agrees with the claimed *cooling down* effect of plasma due to the alumina coating (c.f., **Figure 2** and **Figure 4(a,c)**) in the Al_2O_3/PZT configuration. A consequence of this *cooling effect* would also be the decrease in reaction yield obtained at 5 kHz at ambient temperature and at 2 kHz at 190°C for the Al_2O_3/PZT (0.5%) with respect to the other configurations (around 1.3%) (c.f., **Figure 6(a)**). For these two operating conditions the efficiency of the Al_2O_3 configuration tends to decrease, although still maintaining higher energy efficiency than for the other the operating conditions, especially at high temperatures. The reduction in the mean electron energy due to the lower electric field intensity obtained when incorporating the alumina coating might also contribute to decrease the impact of back-reactions (i.e., ammonia decomposition), and therefore to increase the generally higher energy efficiency found for the Al_2O_3/PZT configuration.

On the other hand, the similar N_2^+/N_2^* intensity ratios obtained at high temperatures for the three barrier configurations suggest that, for the essayed operating conditions, catalytic reaction pathways do not significantly contribute to the reaction, even in the presence of ruthenium particles. The similar nitrogen conversion rates determined for the three barriers (c.f., **Figure 7(a)**) also support this assessment. Only the growing tendency in energy efficiency reported in **Figure 7(b)** for the $Ru-Al_2O_3/PZT$ configuration allows to think about a certain catalytic effect associated to the Ru particles, although its magnitude should be very small or negligible. Indeed, the similar conversions found for the three configurations and the higher efficiencies (see **Figure 7**) found for the PZT and Al_2O_3/PZT configurations support this view.

According to these inferences, we propose that rather than to a catalytic effect of the metal particles (not discarded, but comparatively negligible), the rather high reaction yield and energy efficient values obtained with the three configurations at 190°C (generally higher than recently reported values from literature, see, for example, review publications in refs^{6,54}), should be primarily attributed to the enhancement of plasma

intensity induced by the PZT ferroelectric barrier and the variation of its electrical behavior when increasing the temperature of the barrier.³⁸

CONCLUSIONS

In this study three different barrier configurations (PZT, Al₂O₃/PZT, and Ru-Al₂O₃/PZT) have been systematically essayed to study the effect of the incorporation of a ruthenium metal catalyst in a ferroelectric packed-bed reactor for the synthesis of ammonia. Ferroelectric packed-bed reactors are characterized by high plasma currents due to the high dielectric constant of the ferroelectric PZT used as moderator materials. The operation of plasma reactors moderated with ferroelectric materials, both at ambient and high temperatures, has allowed us to conclude that metal catalyst are not particularly beneficial for the ammonia synthesis under the experimental conditions herein analyzed, even at high temperatures at which a catalytic activity has been proposed in the literature to contribute to the formation of ammonia. We relate the apparent lack of a beneficial catalytic activity to that NH₃ decomposition can be also promoted by interactions with the high-energy electrons formed in the high-intense plasma microdischarges induced by the metal particles. We should remark that this enhancement of detrimental plasma reactions does not discard that the ammonia synthesis reaction may be favored by pure catalytically-driven processes occurring at the surface of the metal catalyst. However, the overall consequence is that the final production of ammonia is similar for the three configurations, and that the energy efficiency is always smaller for the Ru-Al₂O₃/PZT than for the Al₂O₃/PZT configuration and, for certain values of frequency, also for the PZT configuration.

It has been also demonstrated that a pristine alumina coating covering the PZT pellets tends to *cool down* the plasma due to the decrease in the electric field intensity in the inter-pellet space. Additionally, we propose that the alumina coating can decrease the occurrence of inefficient reactions taking place at the PZT surface at elevated temperatures. As a general conclusion, unlike the claims of different studies reported in the literature using dielectrics as moderators^{22,23,25,35–37}, the incorporation of metal catalysts – even activated at high temperatures – in ferroelectric packed-bed reactors does not seem to be the best strategy to improve the plasma-catalytic performance of the ammonia synthesis reaction.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available on line and includes a description of the experimental apparatus (S1), Comsol Multiphysics simulations of PZT pellets (S2), XPS analysis of the Al₂O₃/PZT sample (S3), XPS and TEM micrographs of Al₂O₃ and Ru-Al₂O₃ powder samples (S4), Lissajous plot at different voltages (S5) and the evolution of the consumed power with the frequency at ambient temperature (S6) and 190 °C (S7).

AUTHOR INFORMATION

Corresponding authors

Ana Gómez-Ramírez

anamgr@us.es

Paula Navascués

paula.navascues@icmse.csic.es

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors acknowledge projects PID2020-114270RA-I00 and PID2020-112620 GB-I00 funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033, project TED2021-130124A-I00 funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and the European Union NextGeneration EU /PRTR, projects US-1380977 and US-1381045 funded by Fondo Europeo de Desarrollo Regional (FEDER) and Consejería de Transformación Económica, Industria, Conocimiento y Universidades de la Junta de Andalucía, within Programa Operativo FEDER 2014-2020, and project P18-RT-3480 funded by Consejería de Economía, Conocimiento, Empresas y Universidad de la Junta de Andalucía (PAIDI-2020). The authors thank M.C. Jiménez del Haro, O. Montes Amorín, I. Rosa Cejudo, and F. Vattier Lagarrigue from the Materials Science Institute of Sevilla for their support with the material characterization techniques.

REFERENCES

- (1) Smith, C.; Hill, A. K.; Torrente-Murciano, L. Current and Future Role of Haber-Bosch Ammonia in a Carbon-Free Energy Landscape. *Energy Environ Sci* **2020**, *13* (2), 331–344. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c9ee02873k>.
- (2) Ertl, G. Reactions at Surfaces: From Atoms to Complexity (Nobel Lecture). *Angewandte Chemie International Edition* **2008**, *47* (19), 3524–3535. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ANIE.200800480>.

- (3) Liu, X.; Elgowainy, A.; Wang, M. Life Cycle Energy Use and Greenhouse Gas Emissions of Ammonia Production from Renewable Resources and Industrial By-Products. *Green Chemistry* **2020**, *22* (17), 5751–5761. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D0GC02301A>.
- (4) R. Rouwenhorst, K. H.; Yannick Engelmann; Veer, K. van 't; S. Postma, R.; Annemie Bogaerts; Leon Lefferts. Plasma-Driven Catalysis: Green Ammonia Synthesis with Intermittent Electricity. *Green Chemistry* **2020**, *22* (19), 6258–6287. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D0GC02058C>.
- (5) Wang, Y.; Yang, W.; Xu, S.; Zhao, S.; Chen, G.; Weidenkaff, A.; Hardacre, C.; Fan, X.; Huang, J.; Tu, X. Shielding Protection by Mesoporous Catalysts for Improving Plasma-Catalytic Ambient Ammonia Synthesis. *J Am Chem Soc* **2022**. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jacs.2c01950>.
- (6) Carreon, M. L. Plasma Catalytic Ammonia Synthesis: State of the Art and Future Directions. *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics*. Institute of Physics Publishing September 10, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6463/ab3b2c>.
- (7) Wu, A.; Yang, J.; Xu, B.; Wu, X. Y.; Wang, Y.; Lv, X.; Ma, Y.; Xu, A.; Zheng, J.; Tan, Q.; Peng, Y.; Qi, Z.; Qi, H.; Li, J.; Wang, Y.; Harding, J.; Tu, X.; Wang, A.; Yan, J.; Li, X. Direct Ammonia Synthesis from the Air via Gliding Arc Plasma Integrated with Single Atom Electrocatalysis. *Appl Catal B* **2021**, *299*, 120667. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apcatb.2021.120667>.
- (8) Gorbanev, Y.; Vervloessem, E.; Nikiforov, A.; Bogaerts, A. Nitrogen Fixation with Water Vapor by Nonequilibrium Plasma: Toward Sustainable Ammonia Production. *ACS Sustain Chem Eng* **2020**, *8* (7), 2996–3004. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ACSSUSCHEMENG.9B07849>.
- (9) Antunes, R.; Marot, L.; Romero-Muiz, C.; Steiner, R.; Meyer, E. The Role of Tungsten Chemical State and Boron on Ammonia Formation Using N₂-H₂ Radiofrequency Discharges. *Nuclear Fusion* **2021**, *61* (12), 126046. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1741-4326/AC33C6>.
- (10) Bogaerts, A.; Tu, X.; Whitehead, J. C.; Centi, G.; Lefferts, L.; Guaitella, O.; Azzolina-Jury, F.; Kim, H. H.; Murphy, A. B.; Schneider, W. F.; Nozaki, T.; Hicks, J. C.; Rousseau, A.; Thevenet, F.; Khacef, A.; Carreon, M. The 2020 Plasma Catalysis Roadmap. *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics*. Institute of Physics Publishing October 28, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6463/ab9048>.
- (11) Yan, C.; Waitt, C.; Akintola, I.; Lee, G.; Easa, J.; Clarke, R.; Geng, F.; Poirier, D.; Otor, H. O.; Rivera-Castro, G.; Go, D. B.; O'Brien, C. P.; Hicks, J. C.; Schneider, W. F.; Ma, H. Recent Advances in Plasma Catalysis. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C* **2022**, *126* (23), 9611–9614. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcc.2c03062>.
- (12) Liu, J.; Zhu, X.; Zhou, C.; Du, J.; Gan, Y.; Chen, G.; Tu, X. Plasma-Catalytic Ammonia Synthesis over BaTiO₃ Supported Metal Catalysts: Process Optimization Using Response Surface Methodology. *Vacuum* **2022**, *203*, 111205. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vacuum.2022.111205>.
- (13) Zhu, X.; Liu, J.; Hu, X.; Zhou, Z.; Li, X.; Wang, W.; Wu, R.; Tu, X. Plasma-Catalytic Synthesis of Ammonia over Ru-Based Catalysts: Insights into the Support Effect. *Journal of the Energy Institute* **2022**, *102*, 240–246. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joei.2022.02.014>.
- (14) Gorky, F.; Lucero, J. M.; Crawford, J. M.; Blake, B. A.; Guthrie, S. R.; Carreon, M. A.; Carreon, M. L. Insights on Cold Plasma Ammonia Synthesis and

- Decomposition Using Alkaline Earth Metal-Based Perovskites. *Catal Sci Technol* **2021**, *11* (15), 5109–5118. <https://doi.org/10.1039/d1cy00729g>.
- (15) Liu, T.-W.; Gorky, F.; Carreon, M. L.; Gómez-Gualdrón, D. A. Energetics of Reaction Pathways Enabled by N and H Radicals during Catalytic, Plasma-Assisted NH₃ Synthesis. *ACS Sustain Chem Eng* **2022**, *10* (6), 2034–2051. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acssuschemeng.1c05660>.
- (16) Gorky, F.; Best, A.; Jasinski, J.; Allen, B. J.; Alba-Rubio, A. C.; Carreon, M. L. Plasma Catalytic Ammonia Synthesis on Ni Nanoparticles: The Size Effect. *J Catal* **2021**, *393*, 369–380. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcat.2020.11.030>.
- (17) Akay, G.; Zhang, K. Process Intensification in Ammonia Synthesis Using Novel Coassembled Supported Microporous Catalysts Promoted by Nonthermal Plasma. *Ind Eng Chem Res* **2017**, *56* (2), 457–468. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.iecr.6b02053>.
- (18) Gorky, F.; Lucero, J. M.; Crawford, J. M.; Blake, B.; Carreon, M. A.; Carreon, M. L. Plasma-Induced Catalytic Conversion of Nitrogen and Hydrogen to Ammonia over Zeolitic Imidazolate Frameworks ZIF-8 and ZIF-67. *ACS Appl Mater Interfaces* **2021**, *13* (18), 21338–21348. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acсами.1c03115>.
- (19) Gorky, F.; Guthrie, S. R.; Smoljan, C. S.; Crawford, J. M.; Carreon, M. A.; Carreon, M. L. Plasma Ammonia Synthesis over Mesoporous Silica SBA-15. *J Phys D Appl Phys* **2021**, *54* (26). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6463/abefbc>.
- (20) Rouwenhorst, K. H. R.; Mani, S.; Lefferts, L. Improving the Energy Yield of Plasma-Based Ammonia Synthesis with In Situ Adsorption. *ACS Sustain Chem Eng* **2022**, *10* (6), 1994–2000. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acssuschemeng.1c08467>.
- (21) Navascués, P.; Obrero-Pérez, J. M.; Cotrino, J.; González-Elipe, A. R.; Gómez-Ramírez, A. Unraveling Discharge and Surface Mechanisms in Plasma-Assisted Ammonia Reactions. *ACS Sustain Chem Eng* **2020**, *8* (39), 14855–14866. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ACSSUSCHEMENG.0C04461>.
- (22) Engelmann, Y.; Van'T Veer, K.; Gorbanev, Y.; Neyts, E. C.; Schneider, W. F.; Bogaerts, A. Plasma Catalysis for Ammonia Synthesis: A Microkinetic Modeling Study on the Contributions of Eley-Rideal Reactions. *ACS Sustain Chem Eng* **2021**, *9* (39), 13151–13163. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acssuschemeng.1c02713>.
- (23) Mehta, P.; Barboun, P.; Herrera, F. A.; Kim, J.; Rumbach, P.; Go, D. B.; Hicks, J. C.; Schneider, W. F. Overcoming Ammonia Synthesis Scaling Relations with Plasma-Enabled Catalysis. *Nature Catalysis* **2018**, *1* (4), 269–275. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41929-018-0045-1>.
- (24) Mehta, P.; Barboun, P. M.; Engelmann, Y.; Go, D. B.; Bogaerts, A.; Schneider, W. F.; Hicks, J. C. Plasma-Catalytic Ammonia Synthesis beyond the Equilibrium Limit. *ACS Catal* **2020**, *10* (12), 6726–6734. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ACSCATAL.0C00684>.
- (25) Gorbanev, Y.; Engelmann, Y.; Van'T Veer, K.; Vlasov, E.; Ndayirinde, C.; Yi, Y.; Bals, S.; Bogaerts, A. Al₂O₃-Supported Transition Metals for Plasma-Catalytic NH₃ Synthesis in a DBD Plasma: Metal Activity and Insights into Mechanisms. *Catalysts* **2021**, *11* (10). <https://doi.org/10.3390/catal11101230>.

- (26) Carreon, M. L. Plasma Catalysis: A Brief Tutorial. *Plasma Research Express* **2019**, *1* (4). <https://doi.org/10.1088/2516-1067/ab5a30>.
- (27) Wang, X.; Xu, S.; Yang, W.; Fan, X.; Pan, Q.; Chen, H. Development of Ni-Co Supported on SBA-15 Catalysts for Non-Thermal Plasma Assisted Co-Conversion of CO₂ and CH₄: Results and Lessons Learnt. *Carbon Capture Science & Technology* **2022**, *5*, 100067. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ccst.2022.100067>.
- (28) Bogaerts, A.; Neyts, E. C.; Guaitella, O.; Murphy, A. B. Foundations of Plasma Catalysis for Environmental Applications. *Plasma Sources Sci Technol* **2022**, *31* (5), 053002. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6595/ac5f8e>.
- (29) Gómez-Ramírez, A.; Cotrino, J.; Lambert, R. M.; González-Elipe, A. R. Efficient Synthesis of Ammonia from N₂ and H₂ Alone in a Ferroelectric Packed-Bed DBD Reactor. *Plasma Sources Sci Technol* **2015**, *24* (6). <https://doi.org/10.1088/0963-0252/24/6/065011>.
- (30) Navascués, P.; Obrero-Pérez, J. M.; Cotrino, J.; González-Elipe, A. R.; Gómez-Ramírez, A. Unraveling Discharge and Surface Mechanisms in Plasma-Assisted Ammonia Reactions. *ACS Sustain Chem Eng* **2020**, *8* (39). <https://doi.org/10.1021/acssuschemeng.0c04461>.
- (31) Gómez-Ramírez, A.; Montoro-Damas, A. M.; Cotrino, J.; Lambert, R. M.; González-Elipe, A. R. About the Enhancement of Chemical Yield during the Atmospheric Plasma Synthesis of Ammonia in a Ferroelectric Packed Bed Reactor. *Plasma Processes and Polymers* **2017**, *14* (6). <https://doi.org/10.1002/ppap.201600081>.
- (32) Montoro-Damas, A. M.; Brey, J. J.; Rodríguez, M. A.; González-Elipe, A. R.; Cotrino, J. Plasma Reforming of Methane in a Tunable Ferroelectric Packed-Bed Dielectric Barrier Discharge Reactor. *J Power Sources* **2015**, *296*, 268–275. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2015.07.038>.
- (33) Gómez-Ramírez, A.; Montoro-Damas, A.; Rodríguez, M. A.; González-Elipe, A.; Cotrino, J. Improving the Pollutant Removal Efficiency of Packed-Bed Plasma Reactors Incorporating Ferroelectric Components. *Chemical Engineering Journal* **2017**, *314*, 311–319. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2016.11.065>.
- (34) Navascués, P.; Cotrino, J.; González-Elipe, A. R.; Gómez-Ramírez, A. Plasma Assisted CO₂ Dissociation in Pure and Gas Mixture Streams with a Ferroelectric Packed-Bed Reactor in Ambient Conditions. *Chemical Engineering Journal* **2022**, *430*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2021.133066>.
- (35) Hu, X.; Zhu, X.; Wu, X.; Cai, Y.; Tu, X. Plasma-Enhanced NH₃ Synthesis over Activated Carbon-Based Catalysts: Effect of Active Metal Phase. *Plasma Processes and Polymers* **2020**, *17* (12). <https://doi.org/10.1002/ppap.202000072>.
- (36) Rouwenhorst, K. H. R.; Lefferts, L. On the Mechanism for the Plasma-Activated N₂ dissociation on Ru Surfaces. *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics*. IOP Publishing Ltd September 1, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6463/ac1226>.
- (37) Rouwenhorst, K. H. R.; Burbach, H. G. B.; Vogel, D. W.; Núñez Paulí, J.; Geerdink, B.; Lefferts, L. Plasma-Catalytic Ammonia Synthesis beyond Thermal Equilibrium on Ru-Based Catalysts in Non-Thermal Plasma. *Catal Sci Technol* **2021**, *11* (8), 2834–2843. <https://doi.org/10.1039/d0cy02189j>.
- (38) Gómez-Ramírez, A.; Álvarez, R.; Navascués, P.; García-García, F. J.; Palmero, A.; Cotrino, J.; González-Elipe, A. R. Electrical and Reaction Performances of

- Packed-Bed Plasma Reactors Moderated with Ferroelectric or Dielectric Materials. *Plasma Processes and Polymers* **2021**, *18* (3).
<https://doi.org/10.1002/ppap.202000193>.
- (39) Patil, B. S. Plasma (Catalyst) - Assisted Nitrogen Fixation : Reactor Development for Nitric Oxide and Ammonia Production, Technische Universiteit Eindhoven, 2017.
- (40) COMSOL Multiphysics v.5.5. Wwww.Comsol.Com . COMSOL AB: Stockholm, Sweden 2019.
- (41) van Laer, K.; Bogaerts, A. How Bead Size and Dielectric Constant Affect the Plasma Behaviour in a Packed Bed Plasma Reactor: A Modelling Study. *Plasma Sources Sci Technol* **2017**, *26* (8), 085007.
<https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6595/aa7c59>.
- (42) van Laer, K.; Bogaerts, A. Fluid Modelling of a Packed Bed Dielectric Barrier Discharge Plasma Reactor. *Plasma Sources Sci Technol* **2015**, *25* (1), 015002.
<https://doi.org/10.1088/0963-0252/25/1/015002>.
- (43) Krajczewski, J.; Ambroziak, R.; Kudelski, A. Formation and Selected Catalytic Properties of Ruthenium, Rhodium, Osmium and Iridium Nanoparticles. *RSC Adv* **2022**, *12* (4), 2123–2144. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D1RA07470A>.
- (44) Kruszelnicki, J.; Engeling, K. W.; Foster, J. E.; Kushner, M. J. Interactions between Atmospheric Pressure Plasmas and Metallic Catalyst Particles in Packed Bed Reactors. *J Phys D Appl Phys* **2020**, *54* (10), 104001.
<https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6463/ABCC92>.
- (45) Peeters, F. J. J.; van de Sanden, M. C. M. The Influence of Partial Surface Discharging on the Electrical Characterization of DBDs. *Plasma Sources Sci Technol* **2014**, *24* (1), 015016. <https://doi.org/10.1088/0963-0252/24/1/015016>.
- (46) Rouwenhorst, K. H. R.; Lefferts, L. Feasibility Study of Plasma-Catalytic Ammonia Synthesis for Energy Storage Applications. *Catalysts* **2020**, *Vol. 10*, Page 999 **2020**, *10* (9), 999. <https://doi.org/10.3390/CATAL10090999>.
- (47) Uytendhouwen, Y.; Meynen, V.; Cool, P.; Bogaerts, A. The Potential Use of Core-Shell Structured Spheres in a Packed-Bed DBD Plasma Reactor for CO₂ Conversion. *Catalysts* **2020**, *10* (5). <https://doi.org/10.3390/catal10050530>.
- (48) Whitehead, J. C. Plasma Catalysis: Introduction and History. In *Plasma Catalysis. Fundamentals and Applications*; Tu, X., Whitehead, J. C., Nozaki, T., Eds.; Springer, Cham, 2019; Vol. 1, pp 1–19. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-05189-1_1.
- (49) Gómez-Ramírez, A.; Álvarez, R.; Navascués, P.; García-García, F. J.; Palmero, A.; Cotrino, J.; González-Elipé, A. R. Electrical and Reaction Performances of Packed-Bed Plasma Reactors Moderated with Ferroelectric or Dielectric Materials. *Plasma Processes and Polymers* **2021**, *18* (3).
<https://doi.org/10.1002/ppap.202000193>.
- (50) Bell, T. E.; Torrente-Murciano, L. H₂ Production via Ammonia Decomposition Using Non-Noble Metal Catalysts: A Review. *Top Catal* **2016**, *59* (15–16), 1438–1457. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11244-016-0653-4>.
- (51) Rouwenhorst, K. H. R.; Kim, H.-H.; Lefferts, L. Vibrationally Excited Activation of N₂ in Plasma-Enhanced Catalytic Ammonia Synthesis: A Kinetic Analysis. *ACS Sustain Chem Eng* **2019**, *7* (20), 17515–17522.
<https://doi.org/10.1021/ACSSUSCHEMENG.9B04997>.

- (52) Rouwenhorst, K. H. R. Nitrogen Fixation with Renewable Electricity: Plasma Catalysis as an Alternative for Small-Scale Ammonia Synthesis?, University of Twente, Enschede, The Netherlands, 2022.
<https://doi.org/10.3990/1.9789036554190>.
- (53) Trickl, T.; Cromwell, E. F.; Lee, Y. T.; Kung, A. H. State-selective Ionization of Nitrogen in the X $2\Sigma+g v+=0$ and V $+=1$ States by Two-color (1+1) Photon Excitation near Threshold. *J Chem Phys* **1998**, *91* (10), 6006.
<https://doi.org/10.1063/1.457417>.
- (54) Zhou, D.; Zhou, R.; Zhou, R.; Liu, B.; Zhang, T.; Xian, Y.; Cullen, P. J.; Lu, X.; Ostrikov, K. (Ken). Sustainable Ammonia Production by Non-Thermal Plasmas: Status, Mechanisms, and Opportunities. *Chemical Engineering Journal*. Elsevier B.V. October 1, 2021.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2021.129544>.

Synopsis

Incorporation of metal catalysts in packed-bed plasma reactors for the ammonia synthesis does not contribute to making this technology competitive.

